

Effect of Foreign Exchange Rate on Remittances: Evidence from Bangladesh

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Abstract

The study attempts to estimate the foreign exchange rate effect on the volume of remittances to Bangladesh. Using yearly data from 1976 to 2014, I have employed time series econometric models using three definitions of foreign exchange rate— official exchange rate; weighted average exchange rate against currencies of major remittance sending countries; and real effective exchange rate (REER). The study finds that foreign exchange rates do not have significant impacts on remittances. Other altruistic and self-interested factors such as inflation differential and real interest differential are found highly significant determinants of remittances. Along with these, migration outflow or migration stock, home country's GDP per capita is also found to be a significant factor of remittance inflows.

Keyword: Remittances, Foreign exchange rate, Bangladesh

Introduction

International remittance inflows have become prime source of foreign exchange earnings in Bangladesh. Over time, the remittance inflows have outweighed official development assistance (ODA) and official aid altogether. Remittances help the economy of Bangladesh in multifaceted ways such as building foreign currency reserves, mitigating balance of payment problem, financing capital goods import etc. These inflows play important role in alleviating poverty through raising the level of well-being of the poor (Raihan *et al.* 2009, Khan 2008). In Bangladesh, remittances also have positive effects on nutrition, housing condition, health care, education, social security, income, and investment in microenterprises (De Bruyn and Kuddus 2005, Mahmood 1991, Siddiqui and Abrar 2003, Afsar *et al.* 2002). Multi-dimensional benefits of remittances have also been evidenced across the globe. The benefits include accumulation of human and physical capital, financial development, poverty alleviation, macroeconomic stability, and fall in output volatility and fertility (Adams and Page 2005, Barajas *et al.* 2009, Giuliano and Ruiz-Arranz 2005, Chami, Hakura and Montiel 2009, Naufal and Vargas-Silva 2009). Remittances can work as insurance for migrant sending households against dips in income due to various shocks such as natural calamities, crop failure or economic downturns as well (Yang 2008, Yang and Choi 2007). However, remittance inflows may also have negative impacts because it may erode international competitiveness—the so called Dutch disease effect (Ameudo-Dorantes and Pozo 2004, Lopez, Molina, and Bussolo 2008, Lartey Mandelman and Acosta 2012). Large inflows of

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remittances cause Dutch disease effect in Bangladesh as well (Chowdhury and Rabbi 2013). Foreign exchange rate can be one of the major determinants of remittance volume. Fluctuations in foreign exchange rate may significantly impact on the volume of remittances to Bangladesh. There is a great concern about foreign currency depreciation against Bangladeshi currency regarding slowdown of remittances flow to Bangladesh. For example, after the poll of 'Brexit', withdrawal of the United Kingdom (UK) from the European Union (EU), British pound fell significantly, which created confusion among economists in Bangladesh in that remittance flows from UK to Bangladesh would decrease (Farin 2016). Since remittances play a pivotal role at both macro and micro level development dynamics in Bangladesh, any changes to the inflows may have wider impact on the overall development. Therefore, the study attempts to investigate the foreign exchange rate effect on the remittances to Bangladesh. Rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes a short history of remittances to Bangladesh. Section 3 provides literature review on different possible determinants of remittances. Econometric model is explained in section 4 and findings of the econometric model are analyzed in section 5. Finally, section 6 draws conclusion.

1. A Brief Account of Remittance to Bangladesh

Bangladesh is one of the top ten remittance recipient countries in the world. In terms of remittance receipts, Bangladesh was eighth among all remittance recipients in 2014. Over time, remittances to Bangladesh have taken an upward trend. Since 2000, there has been a dramatic increase in remittance flows to Bangladesh. Since 1980s, the remittances to the country have outweighed the aid receipts and Bangladesh has become a remittance and export dependent rather than an aid dependent country (Figure 1). Currently, remittances account for about 44 percent of total export earnings, the main source of foreign currency in Bangladesh.

Figure 1: Trend of remittances, ODA and export earnings

Source: WDI, 2015, World Bank

According to Bangladesh Bank, ready-made garments (RMG) accounted for almost 81 percent of total export earnings in 2015, thus being the prime subsector of exports. However, if we deduct the value of intermediate goods imported from abroad to produce exportable, remittances might outweigh the net export earnings (since in RMG local value addition is very low). Then remittances could be the single largest source of foreign currency earnings in Bangladesh.

The lion's share of total remittance receipts come from the GCC¹ countries. Saudi Arabia is the top most remittance sending countries followed by the UAE. According to Bangladesh Bank, 59.23 percent of remittances come from this region in the fiscal year 2014-2015. Outside the GCC countries, a chunk of remittances come from the USA, the UK, Singapore and Malaysia. In the fiscal year 2014-2015, remittances from the USA, the UK, Singapore and Malaysia were recorded as 2380.19, 901.23, 429.11 and 1064.68 million USD, respectively (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Decomposition of remittances

Source: Bangladesh Bank, 2016

2. Determinants of Remittances

The basis and extensions of recent studies in the determinants of remittances is the seminal work of Lucas and Stark (1985). In their paper, they mentioned three remitting motives--'pure altruism', 'pure self-interest' and 'tempered altruism or enlightened self-interest'. In the pure altruism motive, a migrant sends remittances back home to smooth household consumption and wellbeing. In the pure self-interest motive, the reasons to remit are aspiration to inherit and invest. The third category includes any kind of contractual arrangements between the migrant and household left behind e.g. co-insurance, exchange-motives, loan repayment, etc.

There is a large body of literature focusing on the micro and macroeconomic determinants of remittances. On the micro side, a wide range of factors such as marital

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status, level of education of the migrants, number of dependents, length of stay in host country, household income level, personal situation and available savings may influence inward flows of remittances (Doorn 2003). Migrants may send remittances for the role of insurance (Cox *et al.* 1998, Gubert 2002). Remittances may be sent to maximize self-interest such as investing in human and physical capital or in small enterprises, repayment of loan incurred for migrant's education in home, and the migration cost incurred during the process of migration (Poirine 1997, Ilahi and Jafarey 1999). One of the reasons for sending remittances could be securing a future inheritance from elders. With this aim in mind, migrants send money in the home country to support elders (Hoddinott 1994, de la Brièree *et al.* 2002, Osili 2004 as cited in Yang, 2011).

On the macro side, economic conditions of the host countries may have positive impact on remittances, whereas home country GDP, presence of multiple exchange rates, restrictions on holding foreign exchange deposits may have negative impact on remittance inflows (Chamief *al.* 2005). Cost of sending remittances, employment opportunities in the host countries; cost of living in the host and home countries; government policies in host and home countries as crucial factors affecting remittances (Barua *et al.* 2007). With increasing overseas employment, remittance flows increase (Freund and Spatafora, 2005).

Economic condition of the sending country may be one of the main determinants for remittances. If economic condition of sending country is bad or hit by negative shocks, unemployed people may migrate abroad to earn income or the existing migrants send more remittances. Improvement in home economic condition also may allow people to migrate abroad as migration requires significant amount of transaction cost. With the increase in income people may migrate abroad seeking for better future as well.

Economic policies and institutions in the home country may exert influence on the flow of remittances. For example, exchange rate restrictions and black market premiums may slow down remittance inflows or may shift the remittance flows from formal to informal sector. These restrictions may also encourage adopting informal channels of remittance transfers (IMF 2005, El-Sakka and McNabb 1999). Tax exemption for remittance income, easing recipients' access to financial services, incentives to attract investments by the diasporas, easing access to foreign exchange, lowering import duties may encourage more remittances inflows (GEP 2006 as cited in Barua *et al.* 2007).

High inflation or real exchange rate hyperinflation may have negative effect on remittances. An increase in inflation in the home country requires more money to be remitted—be it altruism or other self-interested goals. On the other hand, high rate of inflation in the host country allows migrant to send less money back home as their costs of living increase. Financial sector development, which makes remittances easier and cheaper, should stimulate remittances. Political instability or low levels of law and order may deter remittances, since such an environment is not conducive for investment purposes (IMF 2005 as cited in Hagen-Zanker and Siegel 2007). As far as remittances inflows to Bangladesh are concerned, income differential between home and host

countries, relative inflation; relative interest rate and foreign exchange rate may significantly affect worker's remittance inflows (Barua *et al.* 2007).

There is a growing body of literature looking into the exchange rate effect on remittances. Yang (2008) investigates foreign exchange rates shock, caused by Asian financial crisis during 2007, on remittance inflows in the Philippines. During the crisis, most of the host countries of the Filipinomigrants see appreciation of their currencies against the Philippine peso. As a result, Philippine households receive more remittances than before the appreciation takes place. The estimated elasticity of Philippine-peso remittances with respect to the exchange rate is 0.60. Some other studies like Chandavarkar (1980) and Aydaset *al.* (2004) confirm that exchange rate affects remittances flows, while, Swamy (1981) does not find any exchange rate effect on remittance flows.

3. Empirical Models

To investigate the effect of foreign exchange rate fluctuations on the remittances to Bangladesh, I have employed simple time series econometric models. The model is as follows.

$$\text{Log REM} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log M + \beta_2 \log \text{HTGDP} + \beta_3 \log \text{HGDP} + \beta_4 \text{INFDIF} + \beta_5 \text{INTDIF} + \beta_6 \text{Log EXC} + \beta_7 \text{M2} + e$$

Where,

REM= Remittances/Remittances as percent of GDP

M= Cumulative outflow of workers /Migration stock

HTGDP= Host country GDP at cumulative outflow share/ at migration stock share

HGDP= Home GDP

INFDIF= Inflation differential at cumulative outflow share/at migration stock share

INTDIF= Real interest differential at cumulative outflow share/at migration stock share

EXC= Official exchange rate/weighted average exchange rate/REER

M2= Money and quasi money

e= Error term

I have used four models for every specification based on two alternative measures of remittances and overseas employment. I have employed both remittances as in million dollars and as percent of GDP. In regards to measures of overseas employment, the first one is the cumulative outflow of workers and the second one is the migration stock. In the first measure, I add outgoing number of workers in each year to the previous year to get the amount of overseas employment for each year. For all weighted average variable used in the model (under cumulative outflow share) the share of cumulative number of employment for each country has been used as weighting factor. For the second measure, I subtract the number of returned migrants for each year to get the exact amount of overseas employment and for all weighted average variables used in the model (under migration stock share), adjusted cumulative employment--migration

stock-- in each country has been used for weighting factor. In all four models, we have used three measures of foreign exchange rate--official foreign exchange rate of Bangladesh; weighted average of bilateral foreign exchange rate between Bangladesh and its major remittance sending countries; and the real effective exchange rate (REER).

One may argue that there may be reverse causality between remittances and foreign exchange rate. Volume of remittances depends on foreign exchange rate, while flows of remittances determine foreign exchange rate. Therefore, the variable foreign exchange rate in our models may be endogenous and that the OLS estimates are biased. To remove the problem of endogeneity, I have employed the instrumental variable (IV) technique in all of the four models. Data used in this paper mostly came from various issues of World Development Indicator (WDI), World Bank. Detailed descriptions of variables and data are given in the appendix.

4. Estimated Results

Before estimating the models, I have checked for stationarity in the data. In case of time series, if the data are not stationary, then there may be spurious relation between dependent and independent variables. To check the stationarity status of the variables, we have used Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test. After testing for stationarity, I have made necessary transformation to make non-stationary data stationary. Out of the 17 variables, eight appear non-stationary. All of them are difference stationary. Except the weighted average foreign exchange rate variable, all non-stationary variables become stationary with first difference. Weighted average foreign exchange rate is differenced twice to make it stationary (Table 1).

Estimates of remittance inflows at cumulative outflow of workers (Table 2) reveal that our main variable of interest, foreign exchange rate in all three definitions, appears statistically insignificant. With official exchange rate, the foreign exchange rate elasticity is 0.913 meaning that 1 percent depreciation of Bangladeshi taka against US dollar remittance flows to Bangladesh increase by 0.913 percent (column 1). With weighted average foreign exchange rate against currencies of major remittance sending countries, the elasticity is 0.245 (column 2), which is much lower than that of official exchange rate. With REER, the elasticity is -0.283 (column 3), which also confirms declines in remittances due to appreciation in real exchange rate.

For sensitivity analysis, we run the same model for same specifications with different measures of overseas employment and remittances. As before, estimation at cumulative outflow of workers, estimation at migration stock also reports that foreign exchange rates are statistically insignificant in all three specifications (Table 3). Magnitudes of exchange rates are more or less the same as found in the earlier estimation. By using remittances as percent of GDP, I have found same insignificant results (Table 4 and 5). These insignificant results may be because of reverse causality between remittances and exchange rates. To address the problem of reverse causality, I have employed the instrumental variable technique for the four

alternative models. Instrumental variable estimates also confirm that foreign exchange rates are statistically insignificant (Table 7-9). Therefore, all these results show that foreign exchange rate does not play any role in determination of the volume of remittances to Bangladesh.

Turning to the other determinants, migration outflow or migration stock, home country's GDP per capita, inflation differential and real interest differential are highly statistically significant in almost all the models and specifications meaning that they play very important roles in remittance sending decisions of the migrant workers. Sign of migration flow/stock is positive, which is expected, indicates that with the increase of overseas employment volume of remittances increase. Positive relationship between remittances and home economic conditions, GDP per capita, is reported. This indicates that with the increase in per capita income more people migrate which, in turn, increases remittance volume. Arguably, there is inequality in international migration in Bangladesh as outmigration requires significant amount of migration costs. Consequently, with increased level of income, the poor can migrate more. Both inflation and real interest differentials have positive signs. If inflation in Bangladesh increases, then migrant worker will send more money because of altruistic motive or to maintain level of consumption of their families at home. On the other hand, if inflation in the host country falls, then the workers' ability to remit increases as their cost of living falls. Investment motive is reported significant in channeling remittances to Bangladesh as well. If real interest rate rises in Bangladesh and falls in the host country, then interest rate differential widens and the workers send remittances immediately without holding for future gains. However, economic condition of the host country, here measured by weighted average host GDP per capita, and financial development, proxied by M2 as percent of GDP, appear statistically insignificant.

Conclusion

The study attempted to look into the foreign exchange rate effect on remittance inflows to Bangladesh applying time series econometric models utilizing data from 1976 to 2014. As remittances pave the way for development in Bangladesh through a wide range of factors, any change in the volume of remittances can affect overall development in Bangladesh. To boost exports, government manages foreign exchange rate at times. However, this manipulation can take heavy toll on other sectors provided that the action hurts remittances. I have explored foreign exchange rate effect using three definitions of foreign exchange rate in different specifications and find that this effect is statistically insignificant. Therefore, findings of this study reveal that foreign exchange rate fluctuations do not affect the volume of remittances to Bangladesh. In case of bilateral remittances inflows, foreign exchange rate may have significant impact (Byron 2016) but on overall remittances it does not have any impact. Both altruistic and self-interested motives play significant part in determination of remittance volume. Specifically, migration outflow or migration stock, home country's GDP per capita, inflation differential and real interest differential are found significant ones. While financial development does not have any impact on the volume of remittances.

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Appendix

Variable and Data Descriptions

Remittance Inflows: Yearly remittances in million US dollar. Data source: BMET, 2016.

Remittances (% of GDP): Remittances are defined as the sum of workers' remittances, compensation of employees, and migrants' transfers. Annual remittances data, as of June 2016, from World Bank (2016) migration and remittances database are used. GDP data is taken from World Development Indicators (WDI), 2016 to express remittances as percent of GDP.

Cumulative Migration Outflow: Yearly cumulative workers-outflow to different host countries. Data Source: BMET, 2016

Migration Stock: Number of migrant workers, currently living abroad. For detail calculation, see below. Data source: BMET.

Nominal Exchange Rate: Official foreign exchange rate, BDT/ USD. Source: Data source: WDI, 2016.

Weighted Average Foreign Exchange Rates: The Weighted Average Foreign Exchange Rates are calculated as follows.

$$a) \text{WAER}_{t \text{ at outflow Share}} = (\text{OER}_{it} \times \text{OS}_{it})$$

Where,

WAER= weighted average foreign exchange rate.

OER= Official exchange rate, local currency per Bangladeshi taka (BDT).

$i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, $N = 12$ in which number of major host countries is 11 and the left over is the rest of the world. Major host countries are Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Oman, Malaysia, Singapore, Qatar, Kuwait, Bahrain, Lebanon, Jordan, and Libya. Firstly, official foreign exchange rate of each host country is converted as local currency per BDT instead of local currency per US dollar to estimates bilateral foreign exchange rate. For the exchange rate of the rest of the world we proxied Bangladesh's official foreign exchange rate against USD.

t (year)= 1976, 1977,, 2014.

OS=Cumulative workers outflow share, OS=

$$b) \text{WAER}_{t \text{ at migration stock share}} = (\text{NER}_{it} \times \text{MS}_{it})$$

$$\frac{\text{Cumulative workers outflow to each host county}}{\text{total cumulative workers outflow}}$$

Where,

MS (Migration stock share) =

$$\frac{\text{workers cumulative outflow to each host county} - \text{returned workers}}{\text{total cumulative workers outflow} - \text{total returned workers}}$$

Data for returned migrants is not available. Bangladesh bureau of manpower, employment, and training (BMET) records only workers outflow. It is logical that workers migrated many years back will return to Bangladesh and settled down permanently.

To estimate the number of returned migrant, we have followed Barua et al. (2007), where they assume that every six years sixty five percent of migrant workers come back to Bangladesh. Data source: BMET and WDI, 2016.

Real Effective Exchange Rate (REER): We have employed Darvas' (2012) dataset. Methodology of constructing REER index is discussed below.

$$REER_t = \frac{NEER_t \cdot CPI_t}{CPI_t^{foreign}}$$

Where, $NEER_t$ = is $\prod_{i=1}^N OS_i$ nominal effective exchange rate, geometrically weighted average of bilateral nominal exchange rate [between domestic country and its trading partner i]. And the bilateral nominal exchange rate $[S(i)]$ is measured as the foreign currency price of one unit of domestic currency.

$CPI_t^{foreign} = \prod_{i=1}^N CPI_{i,t}^{foreign}$, geometrical weighted average of consumer price index of the trading partners. OS_i is the weight of trading partner and N is the number of trading partners considered. $\sum_{i=1}^N OS_i = 1$, the weight is summed to one. An increase in the index refers to appreciation, whereas a decrease refers to depreciation.

Weighted average host-GDP per capita at cumulative outflow share: This index is calculated as follows.

$$WAGDPPC_{t \text{ at outflow share}} = (HGDPPC_{it} \times OS_{it})$$

Where,

WAGDPPC= Weighted Average GDP Per Capita

HGDPPC= Host country's GDP Per Capita.

OS = workers outflow share (Discussed above)

Weighted average host-GDP per capita at migration stock share: This index is constructed as follows.

$$WAGDPPC_{t \text{ at migration stock share}} = (HGDPPC_{it} \times MS_{it})$$

Where,

WAGDPPC= Weighted Average GDP Per Capita

HGDPPC= Host country's GDP Per Capita

MS= Migration stock share (Discussed above)

Inflation differentials: These indices are constructed by applying the following methodology.

$$\text{a) Inflation differential}_{t \text{ at cumulative outflow share}} = INFBD_t - (INFH_{it} \times OS_{it})$$

$$\text{b) Inflation differential}_{t \text{ at migration stock share}} = INFBD_t - (INFH_{it} \times MS_{it})$$

Where,

INFBD = Consumer Price Index (CPI) based inflation rate of Bangladesh.

INFH= Consumer Price Index (CPI) based inflation rate of host countries. World average inflation rate has been proxied for rest of the world. Data source: WDI, 2016.

Real interest differentials: The indices of real interest differential are constructed applying following methodology.

a) Real Interest rate differential_{at cumulative outflow} = $RIRBD_t - (RITH_{it} \times OS_{it})$

b) Real Interest rate differential_{at migration stock share} = $RIRBD_t - (RITH_{it} \times MS_{it})$

Where,

RIRBD= Real interest of Bangladesh, calculated as deposit interest rate minus CPI based inflation rate.

RITH= Real interest Rate of host country, calculated as deposit interest rate minus CPI based inflation rate. Deposit interest rate and inflation rate of United Kingdom have been proxied for rest of the world as world average rates of these categories are not available. Data source: WDI, 2016.

Log M2 (% of GDP): Money and quasi money comprise the sum of currency outside banks, demand deposits other than those of the central government, and the time, savings, and foreign currency deposits of resident sectors other than the central government. Data source: WDI, 2016.

Export Earnings: The value of all goods and other market services provided to the rest of the world. They include the value of merchandise, freight, insurance, transport, travel, royalties, license fees, and other services, such as communication, construction, financial, information, business, personal, and government services. They exclude compensation of employees and investment income (formerly called factor services) and transfer payments. Data are in constant 2005 US dollars: Data source: WDI, 2016.

Table 1: Test of Stationarity (ADF)

Variables	Test statistics	Critical values (at 5%)	Type	Order of integration
Log remittance inflows	-3.516	-2.964	Stationary	I(0)
Log remittances as percent of GDP	-5.106	-2.964	Stationary	I(0)
Log cumulative outflow	-3.464	-2.662	Stationary	I(0)
Log migration stock	-9.305	-1.688	Stationary	
Log weighted average host-GDP per capita at outflow share	-1.631	-1.688	Non Stationary	I(1)
Log weighted average host-GDP per capita at migration stock share	-1.565	-1.688	Non Stationary	I(1)
Log nominal exchange rate	-0.880	-3.548	Non Stationary	I(1)
Log weighted average exchange rate at cumulative outflow share	0.409	-1.688	Non Stationary	I(2)

Log weighted average exchange rate at migration stock share	0.876	1.688	Non Stationary	I(2)
Log Real Effective Exchange Rate	-1.673	-1.688	Non Stationary	I(1)
Inflation differential at cumulative outflow share	-3.873	-2.964	Stationary	I(0)
Inflation differential at migration stock share	-3.851	-2.964	Stationary	I(0)
Real interest differential at cumulative outflow share	-3.860	-2.964	Stationary	I(0)
Real interest differential at migration stock share	-3.896	-2.964	Stationary	I(0)
Log M2 (% of GDP)	-0.896	-2.964	Non Stationary	I(1)
Export earnings	3.222	-2.964	Stationary	I(0)
ODA	-1.959	-1.688	Non Stationary	I(1)

Table 2: Estimates of Remittance Inflows at Cumulative Outflow Share

Dependent variable is log of remittance inflows			
Regressors	(1)	(2)	(3)
Log cumulative outflow	0.585*** (0.094)	0.494*** (0.102)	0.596*** (0.101)
Log weighted average host-GDP per capita	-0.006 (0.648)	0.491 (0.498)	-0.229 (0.603)
Log home-GDP per capita	2.475*** (0.274)	2.615*** (0.306)	2.432*** (0.293)
Inflation differential	0.086*** (0.024)	0.072*** (0.023)	0.085*** (0.024)
Real interest differential	0.051*** (0.018)	0.052*** (0.016)	0.051*** (0.018)
Log nominal exchange rate	0.913 (0.941)		
Log M2 (% of GDP)	0.436 (0.569)	0.854 (0.599)	0.471 (0.604)
Log weighted average exchange rate		0.245 (0.385)	
Log Real Effective Exchange Rate			-0.283 (0.631)
Observations	38	37	38
R-squared	0.979	0.982	0.979
Durbin's alternative test p value	0.182	0.181	0.121

Notes: The regressions contain constants. Robust standard errors are in parenthesis. Asterisks ***, **, and * indicate level of significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively.

Table 3: Estimates of Remittance Inflows at Migration Stock Share

Dependent variable is log of remittance inflows			
Regressors	(1)	(2)	(3)
Logmigrationstock	0.582*** (0.052)	0.616*** (0.067)	0.579*** (0.050)
Log weighted average host-GDP per capita	0.344 (0.294)	0.349 (0.360)	0.347 (0.329)
Log home-GDP per capita	1.899*** (0.348)	1.790*** (0.446)	1.924*** (0.351)
Inflation differential	0.024 (0.018)	0.021 (0.017)	0.023 (0.019)
Real interest differential	0.028* (0.015)	0.027** (0.013)	0.028* (0.016)
Log nominal exchange rate	-0.064 (0.663)		
Log M2 (% of GDP)	0.197 (0.247)	0.065 (0.256)	0.206 (0.251)
Log weighted average exchange rate		0.288 (0.221)	
Log Real Effective Exchange Rate			-0.116 (0.409)
Observations	38	37	38
R-squared	0.903	0.885	0.905
Durbin-Watson statistic	2.045	1.985	2.044

Notes: The regressions contain constants. Robust standard errors are in parenthesis. Asterisks ***, **, and * indicate level of significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively.

Table 4: Estimates of Remittances as Percent of GDP at Cumulative Outflow Share

Dependent variable is log of remittances as percent of GDP			
Regressors	(1)	(2)	(3)
Log cumulative outflow	0.328*** (0.095)	0.290** (0.123)	0.327*** (0.097)
Log weighted average host-GDP per capita	-0.059 (0.346)	0.163 (0.375)	-0.090 (0.374)
Log home-GDP per capita	0.897*** (0.298)	0.930** (0.356)	0.919*** (0.301)
Inflation differential	0.052** (0.021)	0.047** (0.018)	0.049** (0.021)
Real interest differential	0.041** (0.016)	0.043*** (0.013)	0.038** (0.016)
Log nominal exchange rate	0.335 (0.791)		
Log M2 (% of GDP)	0.459 (0.386)	0.517 (0.410)	0.470 (0.380)
Log weighted average exchange rate		0.445	

		(0.315)	
Log Real Effective Exchange Rate			-0.380
			(0.450)
Observations	38	37	38
R-squared	0.776	0.766	0.764
Durbin-Watson statistic	1.779716	1.653990	1.753 697

Notes: The regressions contain constants. Robust standard errors are in parenthesis. Asterisks ***, **, and * indicate level of significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively.

Table 5: Estimates of Remittances as Percent of GDP at Migration Stock Share

Dependent variable is log of remittances as percent of GDP

Regressors	(1)	(2)	(3)
Log migration stock	0.411***	0.516***	0.414***
	(0.068)	(0.110)	(0.068)
Log weighted average host-GDP per capita	0.103	0.015	0.098
	(0.252)	(0.261)	(0.273)
Log home-GDP per capita	0.080	-0.322	0.083
	(0.464)	(0.676)	(0.479)
Inflation differential	0.033**	0.031**	0.031**
	(0.014)	(0.013)	(0.014)
Real interest differential	0.034***	0.033***	0.032**
	(0.012)	(0.010)	(0.013)
Log nominal exchange rate	0.077		
	(0.615)		
Log M2 (% of GDP)	0.337	0.105	0.352
	(0.277)	(0.299)	(0.275)
Log weighted average exchange rate		0.321	
		(0.211)	
Log Real Effective Exchange Rate			-0.266
			(0.423)
Observations	38	37	38
R-squared	0.541	0.398	0.534
Durbin-Watson statistic	2.028779	1.972331	2.035755

Notes: The regressions contain constants. Robust standard errors are in parenthesis. Asterisks ***, **, and * indicate level of significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively.

Table 6: Instrumental Variable (IV) Estimates of Remittance Inflows at Cumulative Outflow Share

Dependent variable is log of remittance inflows

Regressors	(1)	(2)	(3)
Log nominal exchange rate	-1.863		
	(1.684)		
Log cumulative outflow	0.635***	0.512***	0.635***
	(0.117)	(0.096)	(0.107)
Log weighted average host-GDP per capita	-0.691	0.445	-0.248
	(0.701)	(0.465)	(0.570)
Log home-GDP per capita	-2.228***	2.569***	2.137***

	(0.355)	(0.290)	(0.365)
Inflation differential	0.090**	0.073***	0.103***
	(0.025)	(0.021)	(0.029)
Real interest differential	0.056***	0.051***	0.068***
	(0.017)	(0.014)	(0.023)
Log M2 (% of GDP)	0.501	0.967	0.359
	(0.600)	(0.610)	(0.558)
Log weighted average exchange rate		-0.167	
		(0.918)	
Log Real Effective Exchange Rate			1.905
			(1.545)
Observations	38	37	38
R-squared	0.973	0.981	0.973
Kleibergen-Paaprk LM test p value	0.0532	0.2442	0.0509
Hansen J test p value	0.1107	0.2332	0.0989

Notes: The regressions contain constants. Heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC) standard errors are in parenthesis. Exchange rates in different specifications are instrumented by export earnings and net ODA. Asterisks ***, **, and * indicate level of significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. In the second specification (column 2) the regression does not pass weak instrument and over identification test.

Table 7: Instrumental Variable (IV) Estimates of Remittance Inflows at Migration Stock Share

Dependent variable is log of remittance inflows			
Regressors	(1)	(2)	(3)
Log nominal exchange rate	0.809		
	(0.931)		
Log migration stock	0.481***	0.503***	0.486***
	(0.041)	(0.082)	(0.042)
Log weighted average host-GDP per capita	-0.248	-0.571	-0.437
	(0.413)	(0.656)	(0.347)
Log home-GDP per capita	2.353***	2.261***	2.348***
	(0.162)	(0.286)	(0.175)
Inflation differential	0.047***	0.047**	0.044***
	(0.011)	(0.019)	(0.012)
Real interest differential	0.039***	0.037***	0.036***
	(0.009)	(0.012)	(0.009)
Log M2 (% of GDP)	0.114	0.474	0.142
	(0.459)	(0.797)	(0.476)
Log weighted average exchange rate		-1.250	
		(1.598)	
Log Real Effective Exchange Rate			-0.545
			(0.759)
Observations	38	37	38
R-squared	0.989	0.973	0.989
Kleibergen-Paaprk LM test	0.0364	0.3818	0.0329
Hansen J statistic	0.3687	0.865 1	0.3527

Notes: The regressions contain constants. Heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC) standard errors are in parenthesis. Exchange rates in different specifications are instrumented by export earnings and net ODA. Asterisks ***, **, and * indicate level of significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. In the second specification (column 2) the regression does not pass weak instrument and over identification test.

Table 8: Instrumental Variable (IV) Estimates of Remittance as Percent of GDP at Cumulative Outflow Share

Dependent variable is log of remittances as percent of GDP			
Regressors	(1)	(2)	(3)
Log nominal exchange rate	0.916 (1.663)		
Log cumulative outflow	0.367*** (0.077)	0.391*** (0.102)	0.375*** (0.078)
Log weighted average host-GDP per capita	-0.495 (0.573)	-0.521 (0.525)	-0.717* (0.414)
Log home-GDP per capita	0.813*** (0.268)	0.690** (0.296)	0.799*** (0.299)
Inflation differential	0.070*** (0.016)	0.066*** (0.020)	0.067*** (0.020)
Real interest differential	0.042*** (0.014)	0.043*** (0.015)	0.039** (0.017)
Log M2 (% of GDP)	0.720 (0.459)	1.291* (0.768)	0.765 (0.475)
Log weighted average exchange rate		-1.184 (1.356)	
Log Real Effective Exchange Rate			-0.506 (1.306)
Observations	38	37	38
R-squared	0.936	0.890	0.934
Kleibergen-Paaprk LM test	0.0532	0.2442	0.0509
Hansen J statistic	0.2064	0.8943	0.2065

Notes: The regressions contain constants. Heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC) standard errors are in parenthesis. Exchange rates in different specifications are instrumented by export earnings and net ODA. Asterisks ***, **, and * indicate level of significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. In the second specification (column 2) the regression does not pass weak instrument and over identification test.

Table 9: Instrumental Variable (IV) Estimates of Remittance as Percent of GDP at Migration Stock Share

Dependent variable is log of remittances as percent of GDP			
Regressors	(1)	(2)	(3)
Log nominal exchange rate	2.353* (1.334)		
Log migration stock	0.265*** (0.043)	0.340*** (0.093)	0.275*** (0.044)
Log weighted average host-GDP per capita	-0.308 (0.478)	-1.229 (0.759)	-0.854** (0.364)
Log home-GDP per capita	0.942*** (0.212)	0.617* (0.352)	0.958*** (0.217)
Inflation differential	0.046*** (0.013)	0.049** (0.022)	0.035** (0.014)
Real interest differential	0.030** (0.013)	0.031* (0.016)	0.021* (0.012)
Log M2 (% of GDP)	0.493 (0.465)	0.862 (0.935)	0.586 (0.517)
Log weighted average exchange rate		-1.762 (2.096)	
Log Real Effective Exchange Rate			-1.810* (0.953)
Observations	38	37	38
R-squared	0.935	0.817	0.937
Kleibergen-Paaprk LM test	0.0364	0.3818	0.0329
Hansen J statistic	0.5526	0.4824	0.4713

Notes: The regressions contain constants. Heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC) standard errors are in parenthesis. Exchange rates in different specifications are instrumented by export earnings and net ODA. Asterisks ***, **, and * indicate level of significance at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively. In the second specification (column 2) the regression does not pass weak instrument and over identification test.